

DIVERSITY OF BUTTERFLIES (LEPIDOPTERA: RHOPALOCERA) IN TIRUVALLUR DISTRICT, TAMILNADU, INDIA

Prabakaran S¹, Chezian Y², Evangelin G^{3*} and John William S⁴

^{1,2}Zoological Survey of India, Southern Regional Station, Santhome, Chennai 600 028, Tamil Nadu

^{3,4}School of Entomology and Centre for Natural Resources Management (SECNARM), P.G. & Research Department of Advanced Zoology and Biotechnology, Loyola College, Chennai 600 034.

E-mail: evangelin_g@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The diversity of butterflies in Tiruvallur district, which constitutes of 9 taluks has been studied. A total of 63 genera and 97 species belonging to 5 families were recorded. Out of these, individuals of the family Nymphalidae were dominant with 31 species under 19 genus, followed by the family Hesperidae with 25 species under 18 genus, family Pieridae with 20 species under 12 genus, family Lycaenidae with 14 species under 11 genus and family Papilionidae with 7 species under 3 genus.

Key words : Lepidoptera, butterfly diversity, Tiruvallur district, Tamil Nadu.

INTRODUCTION

Insects contribute to more than half of all the species on the planet (May, 1992) with recent studies estimating the existing insect diversity close to 30 million species (Godfrey *et al.*, 1999). Many advanced insect communities are dependent on insects for their services with respect to nutrient recycling, pollination, seed dispersal, predation, parasitism, etc and they are also found to comprise of a considerable portion of the biomass and energy of the system (Battist, 1988). Moreover, with only one million species being described up until now (Gullan and Cranston, 2009), the insect diversity needs to be recorded in various faunally rich regions of the earth for a complete understanding of their role in the proper functioning of various ecological niches and for accurate estimation of their taxonomic richness.

The order Lepidoptera, which constitutes of the majority of visually appealing insects such as the butterflies and moths have 125,000 to 150,000 described species (Gullan and Cranston, 2009). Butterflies being one of the most studied groups of insects have been systematically documented since the 18th century (Heppner, 1998). India due to its rich and varied topographical, climatic and vegetative conditions and forming a large chunk of the Indo-Malayan biogeographical zone, boasts of a wide variety of butterfly species.

Butterflies are diurnal insects which typically have a slender body with knobbed antennae and broad colorful wings. They differ from moths which are crepuscular or nocturnal insects having a stout body and feathery or hair like antennae. They play a pivotal role in determining the stability of an ecosystem since their numbers can fluctuate drastically with even slight changes in temperature, weather conditions, degradation or pollution. They also serve as indispensable

links in the food web in the many ecosystems and niches they inhabit.

In addition, butterflies have been identified as bioindicators, capable of representing the overall health of the environment (Emily *et al.*, 2008). Before the adult stage the larvae of the butterflies cause severe damage in the agriculture field and plantation areas. Some species that cause such losses are *Euchrysops cnejus* (Pod borer), *Catochrysops strabo* (Pod borer), *Pieris canidia* (Defoliator), *Junonia orithya* (Leaf feeder) (Gaurav Sharma, 2008). Some species of Butterflies play a vital role in food chain as predators of the harmful, *Pita clientella* Zeller which feeds upon pupae of the castor slug, *Parasa lepida* (Cramer) (Vasantharaj and David, 2011).

Studying biological diversity is now increasingly being recognized as a vital parameter to assess the global and local environmental changes and sustainability of developmental activities of various species (Rajagopal *et al.*, 2011). India possesses 1501 species of butterflies (Kunte, 2000) out of which 962 species have been reported from north eastern regions (Evans, 1932).

India constitutes about 84 species of butterflies belonging to the family Papilionidae or swallowtail butterflies, 81 species belonging to the family Pieridae or yellow and white butterflies, 439 species species belonging to the family Nymphalidae or brush-footed butterflies, 225 species belonging to the family Hesperidae or skipper butterflies. With regard to their documentation in Tamil Nadu, 319 species have been recorded in total out of which 19 species belong to Papilionidae, 32 species belong to Pieridae, 94 species belong to Nymphalidae, 97 species belong to Lycaenidae or blues, hairstreaks and gossamer winged butterflies and 77 species belong to Hesperidae (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_butterflies_of_Tamil_Nadu).

Having considerable economic importance, moths and butterflies have been extensively studied in Tamil Nadu (David and Ananthakrishnan, 2004). Notable works on butterfly diversity in India include Tiple *et al.*, 2007; Tiple and Khurad, 2009; Wynter-Blyth, 1957; Talbot, 1939; Soubadra and Priya, 2001; Sharma and Joshi, 2009; Roy *et al.*, 2012; Palei and Rath, 2014; Nimbalkar *et al.*, 2011; Dolia *et al.*, 2008; Menasagi and Kotikal, 2011; Mani, 1986; Manendra *et al.*, 2013; Mandal *et al.*, 2002; Majumder *et al.*, 2011; 2012; Kunte, 1997; Haribal, 1997; Gupta and Majumder, 2006; Gupta and Maulik, 2006; 2007; Gupta, 2006; 2007; Ghosh and Majumder, 2007; Das *et al.*, 2012; Borang *et al.*, 2008; Alfred *et al.*, 2002; Agarwala *et al.*, 2010; Khan, 2011.

Though many studies have been conducted with respect to the demographic population of butterflies, their economic role and diversity in various regions in Tamil Nadu (Sharmila and Thatheyus, 2013; Ramesh *et al.*, 2010; Rajagopal *et al.*, 2011; Gunathilagaraj *et al.*, 1998; Parandhaman *et al.*, 2012), the butterfly fauna of Tiruvallur district has not been studied before. Therefore, the present study is the first attempt of its kind to explore the existing diversity of butterflies from Tiruvallur District, Tamil Nadu.

Tiruvallur District: Tiruvallur district, constituting 9 taluks (Table 1, Fig 1) is located in the North Eastern part of Tamil Nadu with the North Latitude between 12°15' and 13°15' and East Longitude between 79°15' and 80°20' and spreads over an area of about 3422 Sq.kms. Annual rainfall is 1152.8 mm. The average temperature of the district ranges from a minimum 18.5°C to a maximum 37.9°C. The main occupation carried out by the people of the district is agriculture and allied activities with nearly 47% of the total work force engaged in the agricultural sector. The total geographical area of the district is 3, 42, 243 hectares of which fallow land constitutes about 35% and forest area covers about 5.8% of the total area.

Fig 1: Map showing the 9 different taluks in Tiruvallur district.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Preliminary survey was carried out during the day from 7 a.m. to 12 noon for a period of 12 months extending from March, 2012 to March, 2013 with weekly intervals. The different habitats of Tiruvallur district studied include outer forest areas, road sides, fodder bank, orchard planted areas, water reservoirs, rescue centers and agricultural lands. Pollard walking method was followed for observing butterflies (Pollard, 1977). Photographic documentation was done and the data was maintained. Since, identification up to the species level cannot be done with only photographs, additional methods used were survey methods wherein the individuals were collected by plain bag of mosquito hand net. Adult butterflies were collected by sweeping net. Once the butterfly is caught in the net, it is secured as quickly as possible in a fold of the net. Then they are gently placed with their wings folded together, antennae placed extended in paper envelopes of different sizes. Collected butterflies identified up to the species level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 63 genera and 97 species belonging to 5 families were recorded (Table 2). Out of these, individuals of the family Nymphalidae were found to be dominant (Table 3; Fig 2) with 31 species under 19 genus,

followed by the family Hesperidae with 25 species under 18 genus, the family Pieridae with 20 species under 12 genus, the family Lycaenidae with 14 species under 11 genus and the family Papilionidae with 7 species under 3 genus. It was concluded that Tiruvallur district supports a butterfly community wherein Nymphalidae individuals exerting dominance over the others.

In many ecologically stable communities, plants have a strong role in the determination of the structure of the community and the eventual faunal survival in it (McCoy & Bell, 1991). The growth rate of Lepidopteran individuals depend on the host plants with constitute the nutritional composition of the insects (Salnsky, 1992). The majority of insects being herbivores are dependent on plants for nutrition and survival. The phytochemicals released by the plants have a considerable effect on the lives of the insects. The importance of the interplay between the insects and plants assumes colossal proportions in view of the evolution of environmentally friendly pest control techniques. Hence, the decline and abundance of butterflies in many ecosystems is directly proportional to the type and abundance plant growth in the area.

The most important threat to butterfly diversity is urbanization. Complete eradication of greenery in an area drives the butterfly population away since there is a lack of food and reduced chances to increase the progeny. Human activities have an undeniably strong influence on the biodiversity of all existing species (Ricketts and Imhoff, 2003). Even though parks, sanctuaries and other protected areas are specifically kept off limits for humans, the effect of pollution which is a direct result of urbanization nevertheless affects biodiversity. This was also evident from the fact the butterflies were most commonly seen near agricultural and the borders of forest areas and less in areas near human dwellings.

Clark *et al.*, 2007, reported that increased human activities were associated with decreased butterfly species and claimed that the rich, rare and specialized species were the most affected.

Conservation is hence necessary to keep these rare species from being pushed to extinction. The primary work in conservation is the identification of areas or hotspots that support an abundant population of butterflies (Myers *et al.*, 2000) followed by implementation of steps to keep their population from dwindling. Apart from conservation by traditional methods, studies must be conducted to see if man-made structures can help support and propagate species that are seen to thrive only in natural environments. If such an environment could be

put together, it can greatly help in the conservation of butterfly populations.

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Table 1. Locality details of areas where field study was done

S.No.	District	Locality (Taluku)	Total area	Latitude	Longitude
1	Tiruvallur	Ambattur	38.99 km ²	13.0983°N	80.1622°E
2		Gummidipoondi		13.40665°N	80.12380°E
3		Madhavaram		13.15°N	80.24°E
4		Pallipattu		13.33°N	79.45°E
5		Ponneri		13.32°N	80.2°E
6		Poonamallee	6.61 km ²	13.05°N	80.11°E
7		Tiruvallur	10.75 km ²	13.15°N	79.91°E
8		Tiruttani		13.18°N	79.63°E
9		Uthukkottai		13.3367°N	79.9013°E

Table 2. List of butterflies in Tiruvallur district recorded from March 2012 to March 2013

S.No.	Family	Genus	Binomial Name	Common Name
1	Papilionidae	<i>Graphium</i>	<i>Graphium doson</i>	Common Jay
2			<i>Graphium sarpedon</i>	Common Bluebottle
3		<i>Pachliopta</i>	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	Common Rose
4			<i>Pachliopta hector</i>	Crimson Rose
5	<i>Papilio</i>		<i>Papilio polytes</i>	Common Mormon
6			<i>Papilio dravidarum</i>	Malabar Raven
7			<i>Papilio demoleus</i>	Lime Butterfly

8	Hesperiidae	<i>Badamia</i>	<i>Badamia exclamationis</i>	Brown Awl
9		<i>Hasora</i>	<i>Hasora badra</i>	Common Awl
10		<i>Celaenorrhinus</i>	<i>Celaenorrhinus ruficornis</i>	Tamil Spotted Flat
11		<i>Gerosis</i>	<i>Gerosis bhagava</i>	Common Yellow breasted Flat
12		<i>Hasora</i>	<i>Hasora chromus</i>	Common Banded Awl
13		<i>Aeromachus</i>	<i>Aeromachus dubius</i>	Dingy Scrub-Hopper
14			<i>Aeromachus pygmaeus</i>	Pygmy Grass, Scrub-Hopper
15		<i>Ampittia</i>	<i>Ampittia dioscorides</i>	Bush Hopper
16		<i>Pseudoborbo</i>	<i>Pseudoborbo bevani</i>	Beavan's Swift
17		<i>Caltoris</i>	<i>Caltoris canaraica</i>	Kanara Swift
18			<i>Caltoris kumara</i>	Blank Swift
19		<i>Halpe</i>	<i>Halpe homolea</i>	Indian Ace, Ceylon Ace
20			<i>Halpe porus</i>	Moore's Ace
21		<i>Iambrix</i>	<i>Iambrix salsala</i>	Chestnut Bob
22		<i>Notocrypta</i>	<i>Notocrypta curvifascia</i>	Restricted Demon
23		<i>Pelopidas</i>	<i>Pelopidas agna</i>	Dark Branded Swift
24			<i>Pelopidas conjuncta</i>	Conjoined Swift
25			<i>Pelopidas mathias</i>	Dark Small-Branded Swift
26		<i>Potanthus</i>	<i>Potanthus confucius</i>	Confucian/Chinese Dart
27			<i>Potanthus pava</i>	Pava Dart
28			<i>Potanthus pseudomaesa</i>	Pseudomaesa, Common Dart
29		<i>Psolos</i>	<i>Psolos fuligo</i>	Coon
30		<i>Suastus</i>	<i>Suastus gremius</i>	Indian Palm Bob
31		<i>Taractrocera</i>	<i>Taractrocera ceramas</i>	Tamil Grass Dart
32		<i>Thoressa</i>	<i>Thoressa honorei</i>	Madras Ace
33	Nymphalidae	<i>Libythea</i>	<i>Libythea myrrha</i>	Club Beak
34		<i>Parantica</i>	<i>Parantica aglea</i>	Glassy Tiger
35		<i>Tirumala</i>	<i>Tirumala septentrionis</i>	Dark Blue Tiger
36			<i>Tirumala limniace</i>	Blue Tiger
37		<i>Danaus</i>	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	Plain Tiger
38			<i>Danaus genutia</i>	Common Or Striped Tiger
39		<i>Euploea</i>	<i>Euploea core</i>	Common Indian Crow
40			<i>Euploea klugii</i>	Blue King Crow
41		<i>Mycalesis</i>	<i>Mycalesis subdita</i>	Tamil Bushbrown
42			<i>Mycalesis mineus</i>	Dark Branded Bushbrown
43		<i>Ypthima</i>	<i>Ypthima baldus</i>	Common Fivering
44			<i>Ypthima huebneri</i>	Common Furring

45		<i>Orsotriaena</i>	<i>Orsotriaena medus</i>	Nigger
46		<i>Melanitis</i>	<i>Melanitis leda</i>	Common Evening Brown
47		<i>Cirrochroa</i>	<i>Cirrochroa thais</i>	Tamil Yeoman
48		<i>Cupha</i>	<i>Cupha erymanthis</i>	Rustic
49		<i>Phalanta</i>	<i>Phalanta phalantha</i>	Leopard
50		<i>Cethosia</i>	<i>Cethosia nietneri</i>	Tamil Lacewing
51		<i>Acraea</i>	<i>Acraea terpsicore</i>	Tawny Coster
52		<i>Neptis</i>	<i>Neptis hylas</i>	Common Sailer
53			<i>Neptis soma</i>	Sullied Sailer
54		<i>Ariadne</i>	<i>Ariadne merione</i>	Common Castor
55		<i>Rohana</i>	<i>Rohana parisatis</i>	Black Prince
56		<i>Junonia</i>	<i>Junonia atlites</i>	Gray Pansy
57			<i>Junonia almana</i>	Peacock Pansy
58			<i>Junonia hierta</i>	Yellow Pansy
59			<i>Junonia iphita</i>	Chocolate Pansy
60			<i>Junonia lemonias</i>	Lemon Pansy
61			<i>Junonia orithya</i>	Blue Pansy
62		<i>Hypolimnas</i>	<i>Hypolimnas bolina</i>	Great Eggfly
63			<i>Hypolimnas misippus</i>	Danaid Eggfly
64	Lycaenidae	<i>Spalgis</i>	<i>Spalgis epius</i>	Apefly
65		<i>Azanus</i>	<i>Azanus ubaldus</i>	Bright Babul Blue
66			<i>Azanus jesus</i>	African Babul Blue
67		<i>Acytolepis</i>	<i>Acytolepis puspa</i>	Common Hedge Blue
68		<i>Chilades</i>	<i>Chilades laius</i>	Lime Blue
69			<i>Chilades contracta</i>	Small Cupid
70		<i>Zizeeria</i>	<i>Zizeeria otis</i>	Lesser Grass Blue
71		<i>Euchrysops</i>	<i>Euchrysops cnejus</i>	Gram Blue
72		<i>Catochrysops</i>	<i>Catochrysops strabo</i>	Forget-me-not
73		<i>Tajuria</i>	<i>Tajuria cippus</i>	Peacock Royal
74		<i>Horaga</i>	<i>Horaga onyx</i>	Common Onyx
75		<i>Virachola</i>	<i>Virachola isocrates</i>	Common Guava Blue
76			<i>Virachola perse</i>	Large Guava Blue
77		<i>Rapala</i>	<i>Rapala varuna</i>	Indigo Flash
78	Pieridae	<i>Pieris</i>	<i>Pieris canidia</i>	Indian Cabbage White
79		<i>Cepora</i>	<i>Cepora nerissa</i>	Common Gull
80		<i>Ixias</i>	<i>Ixias marianne</i>	White Orange Tip
81			<i>Ixias pyrene</i>	Yellow Orange Tip
82		<i>Delias</i>	<i>Delias eucharis</i>	Common Jezebel
83		<i>Prioneris</i>	<i>Prioneris sita</i>	Painted Sawtooth
84		<i>Appias</i>	<i>Appias albina</i>	Common Albatross
85		<i>Hebomoia</i>	<i>Hebomoia glaucippe</i>	Great Orange-Tip

86	<i>Colotis</i>	<i>Colotis fausta</i>	Large Salmon Arab
87		<i>Colotis eucharis</i>	Plain Orange-Tip
88		<i>Colotis danae</i>	Crimson-Tip
89	<i>Pareronia</i>	<i>Pareronia valeria</i>	Common Wanderer
90	<i>Catopsilia</i>	<i>Catopsilia pomona</i>	Common Emigrant
91		<i>Catopsilia pyranthe</i>	Mottled Emigrant
92	<i>Eurema</i>	<i>Eurema brigitta</i>	Small Grass Yellow
93		<i>Eurema andersonii</i>	One-Spot Grass Yellow
94		<i>Eurema hecabe</i>	Common Grass Yellow
95		<i>Eurema blanda</i>	Three-Spot Grass Yellow
96		<i>Eurema nilgiriensis</i>	Nilgiri Grass Yellow
97	<i>Colias</i>	<i>Colias nilgiriensis</i>	Nilgiri Clouded Yellow

Table 3. Family level distribution of butterfly species

S.No.	Family	Genus	Species
1	Nymphalidae	19	31
2	Hesperiidae	18	25
3	Pieridae	12	20
4	Lycaenidae	11	14
5	Papilionidae	3	7
Total		63	97

Fig 2: Distribution of the existing butterfly families in Tiruvallur district

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